

Results of Criminologist Licensure Examination (CLE): A Baseline Study of Solis Institute of Technology Bulan Sorsogon, Philippines

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Abstract:- One criterion for Filipino educational quality is performance on the licensure exam given by the Professional Regulation Commission (PRC). Based on their actual results from the licensing examination. This study sought to examine the examinee characteristics for the criminologist licensure examination and to evaluate the results of the Criminology Board Examination administered by the professional regulation commissions throughout the academic years (AY) 2011 to 2016. This was done based on their actual results from the licensing examination. This study employed the descriptive correlation method, which involved classifying the data into relevant categories and describing a specific situation as completely and accurately as feasible. The results indicate that Criminal Law and Jurisprudence had the greatest score on the Licensure Examination for Criminologists (41.505), while Correctional Management had the lowest total (33.065, or 58.41 general point average). Criminalistics had a median of 37.275, or 65.85 on a scale of 100, and that value was used. But nonetheless, the examinee profile, which included their age, gender, and GPA, had no bearing on how well they did on the criminologist license examination. To attain the goals of the school administration in achieving a high percentage of passing in the aforementioned examinations, the examinee should use cutting-edge and cutting-edge instructional resources.

Keywords:- Criminologist licensure examination, baseline study

I. INTRODUCTION

Performance on the Licensure Examination administered by the Professional Regulation Commission is one indicator of educational quality in the Philippines (PRC). Students' performance is determined on their actual Licensure Examination outcomes. In order to improve a program's current passing rate and provide a reflection of how well the teaching-learning process is working, it would be helpful to take a deeper look at its prior performance. Perez, C. Passing the licensing exam is a sign of institutions offering high-quality education, according to D. (2015). The Antiojo, LP (2017). Proficiency on the board test for licensure is a result of high-quality instruction provided by educational institutions, according to Visco (D. A.), 2015.

The plans and policies put in place to produce a high percentage of successful licensure examination results track the outcomes of the school's performance on the exam. Imran Tarunet al. The passing rate for the three courses (Criminology, BEED, and BSED) and the four years that the board examinations were held was never lower than the National Passing Rate, according to Al. Ms. Baang (2013) Quiambao, D.T., et al. (2015) claim that the school continuously provides high-quality education, constantly innovates teaching methods, and improves graduates' performances as a source of information for professional development. According to Quiambao, D.T., et al. (2015), a very significant group of predictors for passing the licensing exam included educational attainment, teachers' length of service, the quality of library and laboratory facilities, students' IQ, and students' grade point average. So, these elements must be taken into account while creating strategies to enhance education graduates' performance on the licensure examination. Understand the concept first before moving with practical implementation. The candidates also evaluated themselves for the test through self-assessment. P.T. Chua (2018) Institutions of higher learning should continue looking for professional development chances to enhance teaching ability and professional preparations. Do top-notch in order to aid graduates in finding employment and passing board exams in 2016. MT Cortez et al. The categories of cognitive and emotional ability were statistically significant in predicting likelihood of passing the test. Some famous Higher Education Institutions (HEI) are having difficulty reaching the 60% national passing level and under-performing, according to E. Faltado et al's (2014) Baylan, S. L., 2018 study.

Comparing the examinee's who attended review class to those who did not, the students who attended experienced positive differences for the same time periods, which significantly improved their performance on the board examination. So, it is advised to keep conducting the evaluation as part of the College's intervention program in order to enhance the performance of the graduates. Tan, T.C., (2016) (2016). Additionally, it is necessary to harmonize the various lecturer review materials with the Table of Requirements as set forth in the relevant disciplines and clusters. Tan. (2016), "Excellent performances in Mock Board Examination are not a predictor of performance in the Licensure Examination," T. C. In this context, a strategy was developed to raise the Licensure Examination passing rate. Nonetheless, it is strongly advised that a pre- and post-item analysis be performed on the mock board examination

questions. O. M. Manalo (2013). The value of this Mock Board as a learning exercise to assist students in becoming familiar with the question types and the overall board exam environment. The Mock Board may be a legitimate and useful supplement to board preparation exercises. David T. (2016). Significant correlation exists between performance on the Criminology Licensure Test and GPA and English Qualifying Examination results. Also, the predictive power of distinct composite indices of admission and academic characteristics is nearly identical. An individual to avoid preventing students from enrolling in the programs, it was advised in his study to solely utilize main subject GPA as a screening technique. Garcia, G. C.; Barrera et al. (2013). looked at how well the students performed both during and after their education. Yet, the overall link between examinees' academic performance and their score on the licensing examination is only marginally significant. Examinees' academic standing (grade point average) is not a predictor of whether they will pass the PRC exam.

The socio-economic elements are variables that may impact a student's academic success and exam competence. The school profile varies in terms of curriculum faculty training, and their teaching undeniably, the role of the curriculum enhances instruction and eventually makes the teachers competent, processes students and converts them into quality and great products of education. Munns, Ayden (2012). The model program must be created to provide classroom teachers and support staff with training on how to implement specific support or learning strategies as early as possible, and this training must be based on a program's documented success. This success must include instructional consultation with teachers and the creation of parent and school learning plans. Saquido (2013). While the inferential and critical levels have a positive considerable link with the respondents' score on the mock board exam, reviewees who were enrolled in the review center were found to have an almost negligible to definite but low relationship with the mock board exam. Key words: Board test link with reading, reading skills, and reading comprehension. J.L. Alimondo et al (2013). MT Cortezet. The Licensure Test, which reinforces and enhances their professional dimensions and is also a vital aspect in gauging the quality of education and the system as a whole, according to al. (2017), is extremely significant. So getting through this test is a particularly challenging task. A. Rosales (2014) found that first-time test takers scored better, had a higher passing rate, and had an average rating that was significantly higher than repeat test takers Pachejo, S.J. et.al. (2013) It exposes that there is a very poor association to the performance of the students in the Licensure Examination Performance. Okanga A. A., et al. Al. (2017) found that the proportion of people who passed and were 30 years of age or older (upgraders) was considerably greater than the proportion of people under 30. They also found that the faculty experience and the attendance policy had a marginally favorable correlation with each other. According to Nyangena, E., et. al., performance was reportedly impacted by admission requirements. Al., (2013) found that a mix of school, candidate, and exam criteria were key to a candidate's success in the exam. Foronda M.S. (2017). The mediator

makes the impact of the college entry score on performance meaningful or perceptible. The general weighted average for the first two years is then suggested as the basis for student retention, with the college entrance score as the basis for admission to the program. S. E. Arce et al. (2011). The results of the pre-board examination can accurately predict how well candidates will fare on the licensing test. S.E.S. Baez and others According to at., (2016), there is a substantial correlation between CAT performance and board exam performance.

In line with this, effective schools have consistent mission and focus and make skill development central to their mission. Skills of faculty members in the organization must be reevaluated, there might be necessary for reorganization within the business, and that a seminar on new issues is essential so that everybody will be updated concerning his or her functions, to be at par with the competitors. Therefore, faculty members must be updated to the revised editions of lectures, and there might be a need to surprise students, in a way that will make lectures challenging and participative, not to miss single student to participate in the classroom discussion. R. C. Ferrer et al. Al. (2015) found that the success on the licensing exam is significantly predicted by gender, high school average grade, college entry score, review class attendance, and academic achievement. Men should therefore be given significant attention if there is a tie between male and female applicants for admission. Universities must tighten their entrance standards and retention guidelines. Review classes must be offered to graduates by school administration. The academic results in professional courses are associated to licensure performance, according to De Leon, J. M. (2016).

According to Manabat J.B. Jr. et al., the pre-board exam and graduates' academic success had a big impact on how well they did on the licensure exam. I. and R. Tudy (2014). Educators became interested in knowing more about the students' learning preferences. On a bigger scale, it's crucial that the school take the students' preferred methods of learning into account while revising the curriculum in order for it to be flexible, efficient, and current. According to Dalisay (2014), parenting practices have a significant impact on how developing people build their sense of self-worth. According to the results of his survey, the respondents indicated that their parents are in charge and give them warmth, love, and acceptance in addition to educating them to become increasingly responsible adults.

A. Objectives of This Study

The purpose of this study is to assess the outcomes of the Criminology Board Examination administered by the professional regulating commissions throughout the academic years (AY) 2011 to 2016 and to look into the examinee characteristics for the criminologist licensure examination.

B. Limitations of the study

This study will focus on the results of the criminology board examinations that were given by professional regulating commissions from the academic years (AY) 2011 to 2016 and will also investigate the characteristics of the test takers for the criminologist license exam.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

The descriptive correlation method was used in this study. According to Calderon (1993) descriptive correlation methods when it described a given state of affairs as fully and carefully as possible and where the information was organized into useful categories such as in identifying and categorizing into six areas in the licensure examination for

criminologist; to wit, Criminal Jurisprudence, Law Enforcement Administration, Criminalistics, Crime Detection and Investigation, Criminal Sociology Ethics and Human Relations and Corrections which this study aims to achieve.

A. Source of Data

The source of data in this study are the 566 examinee's of Solis Institute of Technology, Bulan, Sorsogon in the Criminology Board Examination from 2011 to 2016, the study also includes in the sourcing of data with the documents extracted coming from the records of the registrar's office of Solis Institute of Technology (SIT) and from the Professional Regulation Commission (PRC).

Year	Number of Examinees		
	April	October	Total
2011	30	45	75
2012	30	51	81
2013	35	42	77
2014	29	84	113
2015	37	69	106
2016	49	65	114
Total	210	356	566

Table 1: Examinee in the Licensure Examination for Criminologist from 2011-2016

Source: Professional Regulation Commission (PRC), Manila Philippines

B. Data Gathering Procedure

Prior to data collection, permission to conduct the study was sought from all concerned school officials such as the President, Deans, Registrar and the like. They were given the full information about the study including its objectives, the utility of the information, and the treatment for the confidentiality of data. Data were presented as aggregate in forms of percentages and means to maintain the confidentiality of the respondents. The main data gathering tools of the researcher was used documentary analysis and informal interviews to gather the data and other pertinent information. The list examinees were gathered directly from the College Registrar offices and some from the dean's office of the criminology department. Results of the criminology board examination from the Professional Regulation Commission (PRC). The documentary analysis was used to validate the information from office of the registrar and dean's office of SIT, results in the performance of licensure examination for criminologist from professional regulatory commission (PRC) from 2011 to 2016. The informal interview was used to validate the information from office of the registrar of SIT and from Professional Regulatory Commission (PRC).

C. Statistical Treatment

Descriptive statistical tests such as percentage and mean were computed to describe trends across groups and across the subject areas.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Profile of the Respondents

Age, gender, civil status, and grade point average make up the profile of the test-takers, which is divided into two categories.

B. Age

On age. According to table 2.0, the age distribution of examinees for the criminologist licensure test, the maximum number was 274 or 48.40 percent of those who were between the ages of 21 and 25, while the lowest number was 17 or 3.00 percent of those who were 36 years old or older. And 127 out of the total examinees, or 22.43 percent, were in the 26 to 30 year old age range. These findings suggested that the majority of candidates for the criminologist licensure examination are recent graduates of the Bachelor of Science in Criminology (BSCrim) program. As a result, the government should devise a scheme to motivate graduates to sit for the criminologist license exam even when they are 36 years old and older.

Age	Frequency	Percentage
18 -20 years old	123	21.73%
21-25 years old	274	48.40%
26-30 years old	127	22.43%
31-35 years old	25	4.41%
36 years old and above	17	3.00%
Total	566	100%

Table 2: Population Distribution of the Examinee by Age: 566

C. Gender

At the criminologist licensure examination, 494 or 87.27 percent of the examinees were male, and only 72 or 12.72 percent were female, as shown in the gender table 3. Due to the fact that the majority of graduates' careers are held by men, it was assumed that men predominate in criminology programs. The study by Garcia, G. C., provided evidence in favor of this conclusion. Thirty-nine (39) out of fifty-eight (58) examinees, or 67.24 percent, are women in the last four years of tests. According to data, women are statistically more prevalent than men in the field of education. Yet, there is a weakly significant association between test takers' academic performance and their overall score on the

Licensure Test for Teachers. Examinees' academic performance (grade point average) is not a factor in determining whether they will pass the PRC examination. As per Tudy, I., and Tudy, R. (2014). The learning styles of the students have attracted the attention of educators. Studies have looked at learning styles as indicators of academic performance. With the exception of field-dependent for women and field-independent for men, respondents' preferences for learning styles were also identical across genders. In light of this, it may be claimed that the respondents can be simply categorized in accordance with their favored styles.

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	494	87.27%
Female	72	12.72%
Total	566	100%

Table 3: Population Distribution of the Examinee by Gender: 566

D. Civil Status

Table 4, Civil Status, reveals that the data indicated that 475 examinees, or 83.92 percent, were single and 91, or 16.07 percent, were married. This suggests that in relation to the preparation for the examination for licensing as a criminologist, single criminology examinees have more

possibilities to study and review than those who are married. Jove funded this study, which found that criteria like civil status had an impact on how well test takers performed on the nursing licensing examination (LNE), but that factors like age and sex had no bearing on whether or not test takers passed or failed (NLE).

Civil Status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	475	83.92%
Married	91	16.7%
Total	566	100%

Table 4: Population Distribution of the Examinee by Civil Status N=566

E. Grade Point Average

On the criminologist license examination examinees grade point average. Out of 566 examinees who took the criminologist licensure exam, 365 of them, or 64.48 percent, had a general point average between 75 and 80 percent,

according to Table 5. While the lowest was 14 or 2.47 percent, it belonged to the general point average (91 above) percent. The median was 147, or 25.97 percent, of the students who fall within the 81-85 percent general point average.

Grade Point Average	Frequency	Percentage
75% - 80%	365	64.14%
81% - 85%	147	25.97%
86% - 90%	4	7.6%
91% and above	14	2.47%
Total	566	100%

Table 5: Population Distribution of the Examinee by Grade Point Average N=566

Source: Registrar Office, Solis Institute of Technology, Bulan Sorsogon, Philippines

The results imply that in order to achieve the minimum pass rate standards of the Commission on Higher Education, the administration of Solis Institute of Technology should identify programs that raise the GPA from 75 to 80 to 91 percent. This is corroborated by a study conducted by Detran in 2006, whose goal was to calculate Grade Point Average (GPA) using student information. Students from 522.562 LEAs were included in the study. According to the study, family structure has no bearing on academic performance, and there is only a weak association between family size and achievement. In this study by Barrera et al., we found that success on the Criminology Licensure Examination is significantly predicted by major subject GPA and English Qualifying Examination scores. Additionally, distinct composite indices of admission and academic characteristics have nearly comparable predictive power. Andan individual according to his research, it is advised to solely utilize main subject GPA as a screening method to exclude students from participating in certain programs.

IV. AVERAGE PERFORMANCE BY YEAR OF THE EXAMINEE IN THE CRIMINOLOGIST LICENSURE EXAMINATION

The results of the candidates who took the criminologist licensure 11. Out of 566 examinee, 5 are as shown in five tables. In the criminologist licensure examination, 89 out of 17 point forty-nine, or 17.49 percent, was passed, while 467 out of 467, or 82.50 percent, was failed. Moreover, more people passed the exam in 2011 and 2014, while less people passed in 2015.

A. Average Performance of the Examinee in 2011

The results of the test takers in the 2011 Licensure Examination for Criminologists were displayed in Table 6 Between April and October 2011, the Professional Regulatory Commission's Board of Criminology examined 75 applicants for the license to practice as criminologists. In the two successive exams, twenty-two 22 or 29.33 percent of the students passed. On both the April and the October exams, data showed that the national passing percentage was higher than the institutional passing %.

Year	Date of Examination	No of Examinee					Institutional Passing Percentage	National Passing Percentage
		Passed	%	Failed	%	Total		
2011	April 8,9,10	6	20	24	80	30	20%	21%
	October 22,23,24	16	35.55	29	64.44	45	35.56%	43%
	Total	22	29.33	53	70.66	75	29.33%	

Table 6: Performance of the Examinee in the Licensure Examination for Criminologist in 2011 :75

Source: Professional Regulation Commission (PRC), Manila Philippines

B. Average Performance of the Examinee in 2012

The results of the candidates who took the Licensure Examination for Criminologists in 2012 were displayed in Table 7. In the licensure test for criminologists administered by the Professional Regulation Commission's Board of Criminology in April and October 2012, 81 out of 81

candidates passed. According to the results, both for the April and the October exams, the national passing rate is higher than the institutional passing rate. However, the October 2011 licensure examination results were 16 or 35.55 percent better than the October 2012 examination result.

Year	Date of Examination	No of Examinee					Institutional Passing Percentage	National Passing Percentage
		Passed	%	Failed	%	Total		
2012	April 14,15,16	6	14.28	24	85.71	30	20%	32%
	October 19,20,21	7	13.72	44	86.27	51	13.73%	32%
	Total	13	16.04	80	83.96	81	16.86%	

Table 7: Performance of the Examinee in the Licensure Examination for Criminologist in 2012 :81

Source: Professional Regulation Commission (PRC), Manila Philippines

C. Average Performance of the Examinee in 2013

The results of the test takers in the 2013 Criminologist Licensure Examination were displayed in Table 8. Out of 77 candidates who took the board of criminology's licensing exam for criminologists, held in April and October 2012 by the Professional Regulation Commission. In the two consecutive exams, 17/17, or 22.07 percents, were

passed. According to the results, both for the April and the October exams, the national passing rate is higher than the institutional passing rate. The results of the licensure examinations in April and October 2011 were, however, higher than those of the examinations in April and October 2012 and 2013 by 22 or 29.33 percent.

Year	Date of Examination	No of Examinees					Institutional Passing Percentage	National Passing Percentage
		Passed	%	Failed	%	Total		
2013	April 12,13,14	10	28.57	25	71.42	35	28.57%	42%
	October 19,20,21	7	16.66	35	83.33	42	16.67%	33%
	Total	17	22.07	60	77.92	77	22.62%	

Table 8: Performance of the Examinee in the Licensure Examination for Criminologist in 2013: 77

Source: Professional Regulation Commission (PRC), Manila Philippines

D. Average Performance of the Examinee in 2014

The results of the examinee in the 2014 Criminologist Licensure Examination were displayed in 9. During April and October 2014, the Professional Regulation Commission's Board of Criminology examined 113 candidates for the license to practice as criminologists. In the two successive exams, 20/22 or 19.46% of the students

passed. According to the results, both for the April and the October exams, the national passing rate is higher than the institutional passing rate. The results for the licensing examination in April and October 2011 were higher than those for the examinations in April and October of 2012, 2013, and 2014 by 22 or 29.33 percent.

Year	Date of Examination	No of Examinees					Institutional Passing Percentage	National Passing Percentage
		Passed	%	Failed	%	Total		
2014	April 18,18,20	6	20.68	23	79.31	29	20.69%	33%
	October 24,25,26	16	19.04	68	76.19	84	19.05%	43%
	Total	22	19.46	91	80.53	100	19.87%	

Table 9: Performance of the Examinee in the Licensure Examination for Criminologist in 2014 : 113

Source: Professional Regulation Commission(PRC), Manila Philippines

E. Average Performance of the Examinees in 2015

The results of the examinees in the 2015 Licensure 10. During April and October 2015, the Professional Regulation Commission's Board of Criminology examined 156 106 applicants for criminologist licenses. In the two consecutive exams, 12 out of 12 or 11.31 percent of the students

passed. According to the results, both for the April and the October exams, the national passing rate is higher than the institutional passing rate. The licensure examination results from April and October 2011 were higher than those from April and October 2012, 2013, 2014, and 2015 by 22 or 29.33 percent.

Year	Date of Examination	No of Examinees					Institutional Passing Percentage	National Passing Percentage
		Passed	%	Failed	%	Total		
2015	April 10,11,12	4	10.81	33	89.18	37	13.43%	29%
	October 23,24,25	8	11.59	61	88.40	69	11.59%	32%
	Total	12	11.31	94	88.67	100	12.51%	

Table 10: Performance of the Examinees in the Licensure Examination for Criminologist in 2015: 106

Source: Professional Regulation Commission(PRC), Manila Philippines

F. Average Performance of the Examinees in 2016

The results of the candidates who took the Licensure Examination for Criminologists in 2015 were displayed in Table 11. out of 114 candidates that took the criminologist licensing exam in April and October 2016 administered by the Professional Regulatory Commission's Board of Criminology. In the two consecutive examinations, 13 out of 130, or 11.40 percent, were passed. The findings suggested that, for both the April and the October exams, the national passing rate is higher than the institutional passing rate. The

results of the licensure examinations in April and October 2011 were, however, higher than those of the examinations in April and October of 2012, 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 by 22 or 29.33 percent. According to trends, the professors at Solis Institute of Technology should receive training to help them handle professional subjects. Garcia, G. C.'s research(2013) The Field of Specialty subjects have a very high correlation coefficient between examinee academic performance and licensing examination rating.

Year	Date of Examination	No of Examinees					Institutional Passing Percentage	National Passing Percentage
		Passed	%	Failed	%	Total		
2016	April 22,23,24	6	12.24	43	87.75	49	12.2%	23%
	October 21,22,23	7	10.76	58	89.23	65	10.77%	31%
	Total	13	11.40	101	88.59	100	11.48%	

Table 11: Performance of the Examinee in the Licensure Examination for Criminologist in 2016: 114

Source: Professional Regulation Commission(PRC), Manila Philippines

V. AVERAGE PERFORMANCE OF THE EXAMINEES BY SUBJECT AREAS

A. Performance of the Examinee by subject areas year 2011

Table 12 reflected the Performance of the examinee in the Licensure Examination for Criminologist (LEC) year 2011 out of six subject areas on 2011 examination Criminal Law and jurisprudence noticeably got the highest total scores with the grand total of 12.369 scores or 16.492 grade point average while the lowest is the Correctional

Administration 4.764 or 6.352 GPA. Although not much difference in the four subject areas in the examination such as; Law Enforcement Administration, Criminalistics, Crime Detection and Investigation, Criminal Sociology and Ethics and Human Relation.

Subject	Total Scores			GPA
	Passed	Failed	Grand total	
Criminal Law and Jurisprudence	9577	2792	12.369	16.492
Law Enforcement Administration	1864	2742	4.606	6.141
Criminalistics	2427	2843	5.270	7.026
Crime Detection and Investigation	1957	2850	4.807	6.409
Criminal sociology Ethics and Human Relations	1633	3542	5.175	6.900
Correctional Administration	1458	3306	4.764	6.352

Table 12: Performance of the Examinee in the Licensure Examination for Criminologist by subject areas year 2011: 75

Legend: GPA – Grade Point Average

B. Performance of the examinee by subject areas year 2012

Table 13 displayed the performance of the examinee in the Licensure Examination for Criminologists (LEC) year 2012 out of six subject areas on the examination. It is interesting to note that table 13 demonstrates that there is little difference in the four subject areas of the examination,

including Law Enforcement Administration, Criminalistics, Crime Detection and Investigation, and Criminal Sociology Ethics and Human Relation, with a combined total of 20,565 scores or 25,384 grade point average. The data suggested that there was little difference between the 2010 and 2011 examination outcomes.

Subject	Total Scores			GPA
	Passed	Failed	Grand total	
Criminal Law and Jurisprudence	1296	3519	4816	5,945
Law Enforcement Administration	1376	3511	4887	6,033
Criminalistics	1603	3836	5439	6,714
Crime Detection and Investigation	2062	3146	5208	6,426
Criminal sociology Ethics and Human Relations	1458	3573	5031	6,211
Correctional Administration	1381	2506	3887	4,798

Table 13: Performance of the Examinee in the Licensure Examination for Criminologist by subject areas year 2012 : 81

Legend : GPA – Grade Point Average

C. Performance of the Examinee by subject areas year 2013

Table 14 showed the examinee's performance on the Licensure Examination for Criminologists (LEC) in 2013. Of the six subject areas on the 2013 examination, Law Enforcement Administration stood out because it received the lowest overall score, or 5.190 grade point average, with a score of 4.607. However, the results of the other five

subject areas, including Criminal Law and Jurisprudence, were relatively similar. The exam result showed that there is an improvement on the examinee in correctional administrations. Thus, the college dean, professors, and school officials should concentrate on developing measures to further improve the outcome of the licensing exam for criminologist.

Subject	Total Scores			GPA
	Passed	Failed	Grand total	
Criminal Law and Jurisprudence	1706	3061	4767	6,190
Law Enforcement Administration	1290	3317	4607	5,983
Criminalistics	2551	2733	5284	6,862
Crime Detection and Investigation	2169	3048	5217	6,775
Criminal sociology Ethics and Human Relations	1704	3174	4878	6,335
Correctional Administration	1533	3320	4853	6,302

Table 14: Performance of the Examinee in the Licensure Examination for Criminologist by subject areas year 2013:77

Legend : GPA – Grade Point Average

D. Performance of the Examinees by subject areas in the year 2014

The results of the examinees in the 2014 criminologist licensure examination were shown in Table 15. Only criminal law and jurisprudence received a worse overall score, or a 5.716 grade point average, out of the six exam topics, according to the data. While criminalistics, crime detection and investigation, criminal sociology, and correctional administration maintained the same results as

the 2013 examination, law enforcement did not. In order to keep the school's performance on the test, the school administrators thought that the weakest result in this examination related to criminal law in jurisprudence needed to be addressed.

Subject	Total Scores			GPA
	Passed	Failed	Grand total	
Criminal Law and Jurisprudence	1462	4998	6.460	5.716
Law Enforcement Administration	2096	5013	7.109	6.291
Criminalistics	3162	4668	7.830	6.929
Crime Detection and Investigation	3199	4465	7.664	6.782
Criminal sociology Ethics and Human Relations	2221	4716	6.939	6.140
Correctional Administration	1848	5171	7.019	6.211

Table 15: Performance of the Examinees in the Licensure Examination for Criminologist by subject areas year 2014 :113

Legend : GPA – Grade Point Average

E. Performance of the examinee by subject areas year 2015

The results of the examinees in the 2015 Criminologist Licensure Examination were displayed in Table 16. Interestingly, out of the six exam topics, the areas of law enforcement administration, criminalistics, and crime

detection and investigation had higher scores, totaling 19.432 or an 18.331 grade point average. With a lowest grade point average of 17.267, criminal law and jurisprudence, criminal sociology, ethics, and human relations, as well as penal administration, were all studied.

Subject	Total Scores			GPA
	Passed	Failed	Grand total	
Criminal Law and Jurisprudence	1.312	4.669	6.281	5.925
Law Enforcement Administration	1.629	4.852	6.481	6.114
Criminalistics	1.551	5.002	6.553	6.182
Crime Detection and Investigation	1.239	5.159	6.398	6.035
Criminal sociology Ethics and Human Relations	2.026	4.230	6.256	5.901
Correctional Administration	1.158	4.610	5.768	5.441

Table 16: Performance of the examinee in the Licensure Examination for Criminologist by subject areas year 2015: 106

Legend : GPA – Grade Point Average

F. Performance of the examinee by subject areas year 2016

The results of the examinee in the 2016 Licensure Examination for Criminologists were displayed in Table 17. Law enforcement administration had a grade point average of 6.118 out of a possible six, giving it the highest overall score. The lowest overall grade point average, 5.760, was

achieved by crime detection and investigation. Results showed that students performed less well than expected in six subject areas, including criminal law and jurisprudence, criminalistics, crime detection and investigation, criminal sociology, ethics and human relations, and corrections, as measured by grade point average for the 2016 examination.

Subject	Total Scores			GPA
	Passed	Failed	Grand total	
Criminal Law and Jurisprudence	1.633	5.173	6.806	5.970
Law Enforcement Administration	1.548	5.427	6.975	6.118
Criminalistics	1.688	5.126	6.814	5.977
Crime Detection and Investigation	1.493	5.074	6.567	5.760
Criminal sociology Ethics and Human Relations	1.719	4.996	6.715	5.890
Correctional Administration	1.314	5.457	6.771	5.939

Table 17: Performance of the Examinee in the Licensure Examination for Criminologist by subject areas year 2016 :114

Legend : GPA – Grade Point Average

G. Summary Performance of the Examinee in the Licensure Examination for Criminologist from 2011-2016

Table 18 summarized the performance of examinee on the Licensure Examination for Criminologist from 2011 to 2016. According to table 4, the highest score in the Licensure

Examination for Criminologist was 41.505 or 73.33 general point average in Criminal Law and Jurisprudence, Correctional Administration had the lowest total of 33.065 or 58.41 general point average. And the median was criminalistics 37.275, or 65.85 on a scale of 100.

Subject	Total Scores			GPA
	Passed	Failed	Grand total	
Criminal Law and Jurisprudence	16.986	24.519	41.505	73.33
Law Enforcement Administration	9.801	24.866	34.667	61.24
Criminalistics	13.067	24.208	37.275	65.85
Crime Detection and Investigation	12.271	23.740	36.011	63.62
Criminal sociology Ethics and Human Relations	10767	24.231	34.998	61.83
Correctional Administration	8.695	24.370	33.065	58.41

Table 18: Summary Performance of the examinee in the Licensure Examination for Criminologist from 2011-2016 : 566

Legend : GPA – General Point Average

VI. SIGNIFICANT RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE EXAMINEES' PROFILE AND PERFORMANCE IN THE LICENSURE EXAMINATION FOR CRIMINOLOGIST

Table 19 displays the degree of freedom, computed value of X², and coefficient of contingency of the profile, as well as the examinees' performance in the criminologist licensure examination. As previously stated, the computed X² values of 13.90, 64.5, 253.39, 0.37 corresponding to age,

gender, civil status, and general point average are found to be significantly related to examinees' performance in the criminologist licensure examination. The results showed that the coefficient of contingency values of 0.11, 0.36, 0.90, and 0.05 corresponding to the examinees' profile were significantly correlated to criminal law and jurisprudence. This means that in order to pass the licensure examinations, examinees must concentrate on the subject areas.

Statistical Basis	Profile			
	Age	Gender	Civil Status	Grade Point Average
Degree of Freedom (df)	9	3	3	2
Computed X ²	13.90	64.5	253.39	0.37
Critical X ²	16.92	1.28	7.82	5.99
Coefficient of Contingency	0.11	0.36	0.90	0.05

Table 19: Relationship Between the Profile and Criminal Law and Jurisprudence
*Significant at .05 level

Another variable found to be significantly correlated with the examinees' age, implying that their age had contributed to the process of preparing for the criminologist licensure examination. Rosales, A.'s study was similar to the current study. (2014). From December 2006 to December 2010, performance in the eight Nurse Licensure Examinations was analyzed in order to describe how graduates of nursing colleges across the country performed on the tests and to identify the factors that correlate with the examinees' scores. G.C. Rabanal is also mentioned. (2016) conducted a study to examine the performance of University of Northern Philippines Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEE) 2013 graduates (UNP). It was also investigated to determine the relationship between academic achievement and LET performance. According to the findings, academic achievement is significantly related to LET performance. Educational institutions should continue to seek professional development opportunities to improve teaching skills and professional preparation. As a result of the success of the board examination, graduates will be able to find work.

A. Relationship Between the Profile and Law Enforcement Administration

In Table 20, the degree of freedom, computed critical value of X², and coefficient of contingency between the examinees' performance on the criminologist licensure test in terms of the subjects of law enforcement administration are shown. At a significance threshold of 0.05, the estimated X² values of 523.38, 13.93, and 147.87 are significant. Hence, the null hypothesis, according to which there is no significant correlation between the examinees' profiles and their performance on the criminologist license examination, was rejected. Hence, there is a considerable connection.

The computed values of C equal to 0.90 and 0.75 indicate that gender and grade point average are strongly correlated to the performance on the criminologist licensure examination on law enforcement administration, respectively. The values of C equal to 0.20 and 0.33 indicate that age and civil status are moderately correlated to law enforcement administration. This research suggests that factors such as age, gender, civil status, and grade point average may be used to further develop techniques to increase the examinees' knowledge of law enforcement administration and to accomplish educational goals.

Statistical Basis	Profile			
	Age	Gender	Civil Status	Grade Point Average
Degree of Freedom (df)	9		3	3
Computed X ²	4.56		523.39*	13.93
Critical X ²	7.82		7.82	16.92
Coefficient of Contingency	0.20		0.90*	0.33

Table 20: Relationship between the Profile and Law Enforcement Administration

*Significant at .05 level

B. Relationship Between the Profile and Criminalistics

The degree of freedom, estimated critical value of X² and coefficient of contingency between the examinees' profiles and their performance in terms of criminalistics subject areas are shown in Table 21. Age, gender, civil status, and grade point average are not connected with performance on the criminalistics topics portion of the licensure examination, according to the computed value of X² equal to 10.97, 9.93, 11.14, and 25.27. One variable has a moderately high coefficient of contingency of 0.42, indicating this.

According to the findings, having complete faith in the subject matter they learn was highly influenced by the profile. The analysis of the data also suggests that the enhancement program updates and complements the knowledge of the test takers on the most recent changes to the examinations. It also indicates that during the enhancement program, new knowledge can be incorporated, which will improve the learner's experience. The two are hence significantly related.

Statistical Basis	Profile			
	Age	Gender	Civil Status	Grade Point Average
Degree of Freedom (df)	2		3	9
Computed X ²	10.07*		9.93*	11.14*
Critical X ²	5.99		7.82	16.92
Coefficient of Contingency	0.02		0.28	0.09

Table 21: Relationship Between the Profile and Criminalistics

*Significant at .05 level

C. Relationship Between the Profile and Crime Detection and Investigation

Table 22 presented the degree of freedom, critical and computed values of X² and the coefficient of contingency of the examinees profile and the performance in licensure examination for criminologist in terms of crime detection and investigation subject areas. As noted, the values of computed X² equal to 17.40, 8.69, 21.62 and 16.06 corresponding to age, gender, civil status, grade point average are found to be significantly related with crime detection and investigation.

Results revealed that values of 0.36, 0.26, 0.40 and 0.35 corresponding to the profile of the examinees are significantly correlated to crime detection and investigation. This means that the examinees are motivated to take the licensure exams for criminologist. Findings imply that the profile and performance of the licensure examination contribute to augment the new knowledge and understanding its implication on the educational process. The age of the examinees is another variable was found to be significantly correlated with the result in crime detection and investigation performance in the licensure examination for criminologist. This means that their age are had contributed to the performance of the examinees.

Statistical Basis	Profile			
	Age	Gender	Civil Status	Grade Point Average
Degree of Freedom (df)	3		3	9
Computed X ²	17.40*		8.69*	21.62
Critical X ²	7.82		7.82	16.92
Coefficient of Contingency	0.36		0.26	0.40

Table 22: Relationship Between the Profile and Crime Detection and Investigation

*Significant at .05 level

D. Relationship Between the Profile and Criminal Sociology Ethics and Human Relations

As shown in Table 23 are degree of freedom, critical and computed X^2 and the coefficient of contingency between the examinee profile and the performance in the licensure examination for criminologist in terms of criminal sociology ethics and human relations. The researcher rejected the null hypothesis, according to which there is no significant correlation between the examinee' profile and their performance on the criminologist licensure examination, as a result of the computed values of X^2 equal to 64.42. One variable has a moderately positive correlation,

as shown by values of the coefficient of contingency equal to 0.60. However, it was discovered that the coefficient values of 0.30, 0.05, and 0.07 did not significantly correlate with criminal sociology, ethics and human relations. It shows that the examinee profile, including their age, gender, and grade point average, had no impact on how well they performed on the criminologist license examination. Examinee should use cutting-edge and cutting-edge instructional resources to achieve the goals of the school administration in creating a high percentage of passing in the aforementioned examinations, but they shouldn't overdo it.

Statistical Basis	Profile			
	Age	Gender	Civil Status	Grade Point Average
Degree of Freedom (df)	9	3	3	3
Computed X^2	11.21	6.30	64.62	8.82
Critical X^2	16.92	7.82	7.82	7.29
Coefficient of Contingency	0.30	0.05	0.60	0.07

Table 23: Relationship Between the Profile and Criminal Sociology Ethics and Human Relations

*Significant at .05 level

Table 24 are the degree of freedom, critical and computed values of X^2 and the contingency of the examinee profile and the performance in the licensure examination for criminologist. It has been demonstrated that the values of computed X^2 equal to 4.72, 5.91, 6.70, and 6.94, respectively, corresponding to age, gender, civil status, and grade point average, are significantly associated to

corrections. Also, it was observed that civil status, gender, and age have a substantial impact on corrections, with values of the contingency coefficient finding to be 0.23, 0.22, and 0.20. This suggests that age and civil status are factors that affect how well candidates perform on the criminologist license examination.

Statistical Basis	Profile			
	Age	Gender	Civil Status	Grade Point Average
Degree of Freedom (df)	3	3	9	3
Computed X^2	4.72	5.91	6.70	6.94
Critical X^2	7.82	7.82	16.92	7.29
Coefficient of Contingency	0.20	0.22	0.23	0.05

Table 24: Relationship Between the Profile and Correctional Administration

*Significant at .05 level

VII. CONCLUSIONS

The faculty strength at Solis Institute of Technology's criminology department was in criminal law and jurisprudence, while the identified weakness was in correctional administration. As a result, the Solis Institute of Technology administration (SIT) should hire faculty with specialization in correctional administration to improve graduate performance on the criminologist licensure examination. The school administration be encouraged to develop a creative program to improve the number of graduates who pass the criminologist licensure examinations. That the Policy Standard Guidelines for Criminology Education and Table of Specifications should be used to re-evaluate the curriculum and course syllabi by the school curriculum committee, the admission policy must implement a more stringent selection process for entrance and retention, and must give graduating students in-depth tests to identify their course-related strengths and weaknesses. A tracer study of graduates from the

criminology program should be carried out by the office of alumni affairs.

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